

CitySCAPE

Risk analysis and impact assessment engine

Financial impact assessment engine

Collaborative threat investigation platform

The CitySCAPE Solution

CitySCAPE introduces innovative risk analysis techniques and orchestrates a number of software solutions to realize an interoperable toolkit that seamlessly integrates to any multimodal transport system.

More specifically, the CitySCAPE software toolkit will:

- Detect suspicious traffic-data values and identify persistent threats
- Evaluate an attack's impact in both technical and financial terms
- Combine external knowledge and internally-observed activities to enhance the predictability of zero-day attacks
- Instantiate a networked overlay to circulate informative notifications to CERT/CSIRT authorities and support their interplay.

CitySCAPE At a Glance

Consortium

AIRBUS

EUROPEAN DYNAMICS

kaspersky

Tallinn

REPUBLIC OF ESTONIA
INFORMATION SYSTEM AUTHORITY

AMT
MOBILITÀ E
INNOVAZIONE

STAM
MASTERING EXCELLENCE

Gruppo SIGLA
esperienza ed innovazione

UNIVERSITY OF PIRAEUS
RESEARCH CENTER

OPPIDA
EXPERT IN SECURITY
DESIGN OF INFORMATION

AUSTRIAN
STANDARDS
Driven by Making Sense

GS
GROUP

ENGINEERING

TAL
TECH

Project Facts

- **Duration:** 36 months (September 2020-August 2023)
- **EU funding:** 4 998 057.88 €
- **Pilots:** Tallinn, Estonia / Genova, Italy
- **Project Coordinator:** Dr Angelos Amditis, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) a.amditis@iccs.gr

